

**DETERMINANTS OF THE SUSTAINABILITY OF MICRO AND
SMALL ENTERPRISES:
THE CASE OF MSEs IN REBUGEBEYA TOWN**

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Acronyms and Abbreviations

SWWTO	Sinan woreda work and training office
MSEs	Micro and small enterprises
SMSE	Sustainability of Micro and Small Enterprises
FDRE	Federal Democratic Republic of Ethiopia
ILO	International Labor Organization
NGOs	Non-Governmental Organizations
SPSS	Statistical package Software for Social Science
USAID	United States Agency for International Development
UN	United Nation
ANRS	Amhara National Regional State
SDGs	Sustainable Development Goals

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Abstract

The aim of this research was to explore the determinant factors of Micro and Small Enterprises sustainability in Rebu Gebeya Town. To achieve the desired goal of this study the researcher used explanatory research design and a mixture of quantitative and qualitative data analyzing method. The sample techniques were stratified random sampling and purposive sampling methods. A stratified random sampling method was prepared for Enterprises whereas a purposive sampling technique was used for the office heads, team leader and expert of Micro and Small Enterprises development office. The number of questions prepared for enterprises was 253 whereas the interview delivered to the office heads, team leader and experts of the office and the document review also analyzed. The collected data were analyzed using SPSS (Statistical product Software for Social Science) Version 23. Presentation, interpretation and discussions were concluded in line with regression and correlation results using table, percentage to get ample findings. The finding of the study revealed that management factors, financial factors, work related factors, technological factors, marketing factors and political factors are very critical to make Micro and Small Enterprises activity unsustainable. Besides, the management factors which have a beta of 0.994 coefficient and has high effect on micro and small enterprises sustainability, followed by the financial factors, marketing factors, work related factors, political-legal and technological factors of the enterprises. And finally, to guarantee the sustainability of the micro and small enterprises woreda work and training office, and other concerned bodies should work together to solve sustainability problems and to promote the development and expansion of micro and small enterprise development programs.

Key Words: *micro and small enterprise, sustainability, determinants, work and training Office*

CHAPTER ONE

INTRODUCTION

1.1 Background of the Study

The definition and types of micro and small enterprises are different from country to country and there is no universally stated meaning for micro and small enterprises. MSEs are a way of which accelerated economic growth and rapid industrial expansion have been achieved Harris et al.,(2006). In federal democratic republic of Ethiopia, MSEs are the second largest employment generating sector next to agriculture CSA, (2007). According to Lepi, (2005) The involvement of Micro and Small Enterprises around the world has become unquestionable and especially in developing countries, where development in this sector is seen as a key strategy for economic growth, job generation and poverty reduction Agupusi, (2007)According to (Muiruri, 2017). Micro and Small Enterprises have become engines of poverty reduction, job creation and business development among others in various developed and developing countries. In the current world economy, micro and small enterprises progressively being regarded as a way for economic development of most economic systems. Industrial development policy authorities in most developing countries globally have realized the significant share made by MSEs towards attainment of sustainable local economic development and impoverishment through creation of employment opportunities (Fekede, 2019). The dynamic function of micro and small enterprises in developing countries as engines through which the growth objectives can be achieved Ibrahim, et al., (2008). Furthermore small scale business has been recognized as a feeder service to large- scale industries Fabayo, (2009). They may starting line as micro and grow into small, medium and large corporations if well nurtured Colli, et al., (2005).Past studies in the developing countries of South Asia have indicated that, MSEs constitute over 97 percent and contribute between 40–60 percent of the total output or value-added to their national economies. While most of the MSEs are located in rural areas and they account for over 70 percent of total employment (Fan 2005; Kamesam 2003; Nepal et al., 2002; Shrestha 2005). This makes MSEs a major field of business concern for government and nongovernment organizations with an objective of unemployment reduction, income generation and equitable income distribution, import substitution, innovation, poverty alleviation Habtamu et al., (2013).Furthermore, according to Mead and Liedholm(2009), the MSE activities can contribute to increasing tax-incomes for the government and enable the government in the long run to invest the money. Christie and Crompton (2002) point out that micro and small business hold up to 70 percent of businesses. In developing nations, these numbers could be higher as

micro and small Enterprises (MSEs) are widely recognized the world over for their role in the societal, political and economic development.

The sector brings economic change by effectively using the skill and the talent of the citizens without requesting high-level training, much capital and advanced technology Habtamu ,et al.(2013). The major challenges facing African MSEs are; Access to financing; infrastructure like Electricity supply, water supply, road accessibility and sheds for manufacturing and selling; Poor management; Competency and capability; Negative perception; Access to reliable information; Government support; Corruption; Other challenges facing MSEs in Africa include: political instability, labor issues due to lack of established legal frameworks, lack of coordination, ethnic violence destructions and lack of qualified personnel Bowen et al., 2009; Katua.,(2014).

Currently Ethiopia implementing a Ten-year (2013-2022 E.C) Economic Transformation Plan in line with its long-term vision of achieving rapid, sustainable and equitable socioeconomic growth and development, reducing poverty, and meeting the Millennium sustainability Goals (MSGs) within the framework of macroeconomic stability. However, the great number of MSEs are ineffective to grow as expected (expand in terms of employment) and remain to be survival (non-growing) type which cannot provide employment Habtamu et al., (2013). According to Gebreyesus,(2007), out of 1000 MSEs around 69% of the enterprises are found survival type in Ethiopia Wasihun and Paul, (2010) reported that, (75.6%) of the MSEs are unable to grow and only 21.9% of the MSEs were added workers in Addis Ababa. The role of micro and small businesses to development are generally acknowledged, enterprises look many obstacles that limit their long-term survival and development. Studies on micro and small enterprises development has shown that the rate of failure in developing countries is higher than in the developed world (Arinaitwe, 2002). Knowing that the sustainability of micro and small enterprises in the research area out of 876 MSEs around 31 % of the enterprises are found to be unable to grow. In the research area the development of micro and small enterprises is being done extensively, especially for the last GTP I and II the sector played a significant role in providing jobs and creating profits that bring income to the individuals. Accordingly, this study will try to explore the sustainable ways and contributions of micro and small enterprises in Sinan Woreda Administration. The study will give emphasis to understand and investigate the determinant factors that would influence the sustainability of micro and small enterprises in Rebu Gebeya Town.

1.2 Statement of the problem

Currently, many countries exercise MSEs in order to promote entrepreneurship, investment and growth, facilitating access to venture capital, cutting administrative burdens and increasing legal certainty. Likewise, Micro and Small Enterprise Sectors contribute to the economy of countries' by creating employment opportunities, production of goods and services and other value added activities. Considering this, the government of Ethiopia has been issued Micro and Small Enterprises Strategy FDRE, MoTI, (1997) by recognizing the potential role of the sector as a key factor for rapid economic development and unemployment reduction. In addition to the existing ten year economic transformation Plan, Ethiopia has envisaged the promotion of micro and small enterprises as an important tool of poverty reduction FDRE, MoFED, (2010). According to World bank (2004) even if the micro and small enterprises had the possibilities to contribute to the development of the country's economy, the sector in most developing countries look constraints both at their beginning and in the functioning phase. Different written works showed that, three-fourth of the MSEs in rural Tanzania is non-growing due to the problem of access to finance, road infrastructure and communication Kinda andLoening, (2008). In addition, majority of MSEs in Eldoret, Kenya has experienced minimal or no growth due to the inadequacy of availability of finances, poor business management skills, poor marketing and entrepreneurial attribute of the owner managers Mbugua et al., According to Mulu Gebreeyesus(2007) the study indicates that, the average annual growth of the surveyed six major towns in Ethiopia was 9 percent since start-up and 69 percent of these MSEs did not show growth due to the problems of inadequate formal source of credit and informal network. The work of Abebayehu (2016) indicates that the major challenges that affect performance of small enterprises are working premises, access to finance, access to network, technology and ease of regulation. Many studies have done important jobs to illustrate the nature, operation and contribution of MSEs at large and their contributions to local economic development in particular. However, such studies take the issues of MSEs with little focus on their value chains. For instance, Admasu, (2012) reported that most MSEs have no growth and remain at their initial level due to different internal (owner's related and/or firm's related) and external factors .Almost all of this studies were concentrated Addis Abeba, and in some other large city. And also they depend on its purpose and how microfinance promoted MSEs. Finally, limited researches are conducted in the research title regarding to identify determinants for the sustainability of MSEs in the country as well as in the region. Therefore, to identify the determinants of the sustainability of MSEs in the study area demands to identify. Those sustainability measures has been identified too and has used by government and non-government institution to develop MSEs in

continuous manner. Uninterrupted studies and recommendations on determinants of sustainability of MSEs is mandatory.

The following gaps were taken into account when the investigator was inspired to investigate this topic. In earlier research on the subject related to specific factors, such as financial, market and infrastructural factors that are explained the only factors that affect the enterprises growth and sustainability rather than variables determining micro and small enterprises sustainability across in the Ethiopia. This can drive the results to be interpreted incorrectly. Since several areas and enterprises may have different determining variables. As far as the researcher finds the research no research has been done on this subject in the area under study. This suggests that the determinants may vary depending on the geography, work culture, level of economy, employment rate and attitudes of the society in each location. In many research works the majority of them adopt a qualitative or quantitative strategy, but this study will adopt an alternative strategy that is a mixed methodology both qualitative and quantitative to get specific information from a variety of data collection techniques. Others employed the descriptive approach; however, in this case, both the explanatory and descriptive approaches will be used. This study covers both internal and external determinants that influence the sustainability of micro and small enterprises. Since it is thought that micro and small enterprises sustainability is influenced by different factors, unlike every other researcher who only includes external determinants in their study. This study will close the gap in the body of literature on the subject by addressing the aforementioned gap.

1.3 Research Questions

The study answered the following research questions:

- To what extent do internal determinants influence the sustainability of micro and small enterprises?
- To what extent do external determinants influence the sustainability of micro and small enterprises?

1.4 Objectives of the Study

1.4.1. General Objective of the Study

The overall objective of this study is to examine the determinants of micro and small enterprise sustainability in Rebu Gebeya Town.

1.4.2 Specific Objectives of the Study

In addition to the general objective, this study addresses the following specific objectives:

1. To examine the effect of internal determinants that influences the sustainability of micro and small enterprises.
2. To determine the effect of external determinants that influences the sustainability of micro and small enterprises.

1.5 Significance of the Study

Accordingly, the outcome of this study has the following benefits.

First, the research finding will help Sinan Woreda Administration especially Woreda Work and Training Office can understand the actual level of micro and small enterprise development activities and the factors that affect micro and small enterprises and also help them to follow the possible direction or ways and adjustments for improvements of micro and small enterprises sustainability.

Secondly, it helps the investigator to acquire knowledge and gain practical experience on the issue raised in the study, and also for the partial fulfillment of the requirement for master degree in study area.

Thirdly, the study intends to investigate the growth level and transition of MSEs and their sustainability determinants in the study area. Moreover, the research has significant importance for local decision-makers to evaluate and to take corrective measures to overcome the challenges for their sustainability.

Finally, the finding of the study will also be used as a stepping-stone for other researchers to conduct further research on the subject matter.

So, this research investigates for the determinants of sustainability of MSEs in Sinan woreda Administration

1.6 Scope of the Study

This research mainly deals about examining the determinants that affect micro and small enterprises sustainability in Rebu Gebeya Town. The delimit of the study is based on time, thematic and geographic conditions. The main purposes of this study will be engaged towards investigating and answering the question for determinants of micro and small enterprises sustainability and their

contribution to community-based development. Although, there are different issues that should be researched in relation to determinants for sustainability of MSEs, this study was limited to the technological, management, marketing, financial, work related and political factors. Besides, the study was represent all MSEs that are legally registered & functioning in the study area and in the research period. The study only concentrates on Sinan Woreda Administration work and training Office especially in Rebu Gebeya Town is the geographical coverage of the study to come with findings. This study will use mixed research approach and descriptive design.

1.7 Limitation of the Study

Since as a human being everybody may not achieve effectively what he/she plans to do due to certain unexpected internal as well as external problems. Hence, this research is not without limitation and exhaustive. Hence, in undertaking this research one of the major problems that the researcher encounters was unable to collect data from the whole population. However, despite these limitations, this thesis is done in adherence to the research objective of the study.

Thus, the researcher contacts valuable individual respondents to overcome the bottlenecks. Finally, the researcher was scarce in financial resource and time to undertake the research study.

1.8 Operational definitions of key terms

Micro enterprises: are business enterprises found in all sectors of the economy with a paid-up capital (fixed assets) of not more than Birr 600,000, birr for industry and 400,000 birr for service sector and having 10 employees/members/ but excluding high-tech consultancy firms and other high-tech establishments.

Small enterprises: those business enterprises with paid-up capital of above 600,000 birr and not exceeding birr 10,000,000 for industry and above 400,000 birr and not exceeding birr 5,000,000 for service sector and having 11-50 employees/members/ and excluding high technology consultancy firms and other high technology establishments.

Enterprise: it refers to an undertaking engaged in production and/or distribution of goods & services for commercial benefits, beyond subsistence (household) consumption at the household level.

Sustainability: is the ability to exist constantly and it is also the process of people maintaining changes in homeostasis balanced environmental conditions in which the exploitation of resources, the direction of investments, the orientation of technological development, and institutional change are all in harmony and enhance both current and future potential to meet human needs and aspirations. It also

refers to the ability of the enterprises to continuously maintain in the business environment. Source (rahelfitane)

Determinants: are factors or cause that makes something happen or leads directly to a decision. In the research area context it is a factor which is influencing aspects such as management, market, finance, technology, work-related and political support issues that affect sustainability of MSEs

Enterprise: can be defined as an undertaking engaged in production and/or distribution of goods & services for commercial benefits, beyond subsistence (household) consumption at the household level.

Factors: A factor is a contributory aspect such as government regulation, business information service, and management experience, marketing and financial management influences that affect performance of micro and small enterprises.

Work and Training Office: it is an institution which plans to spark industrial revolution by implementing the strategies and plans in the MSE activities.

1.9 Organization of the Paper

The total body of the paper organized in five chapters. The first chapter outlines the introduction part in order to announce my topic provide context rational for my work before stating my research questions and the parting include with the background of the study, statement of the problem, questions, significance of the study, and objectives of the study, limitation and organization of the study. The second chapter deals about the review of related literature which includes both the theoretical, empirical literatures and conceptual framework of the study and research hypothesis. The third chapter is about research methodology, which tells us about the description of the study area, research approach, research design, population and sample, data source, data collection procedures, ethical considerations and data analysis. Chapter four concentrates on data presentation, analysis, and interpretation. Finally, chapter five contains summary of findings, conclusion and recommendations.

CHAPTER TWO

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

2.1 Introduction

In this chapter both the theoretical as well as empirical literature related to the overall themes of the study are reviewed. It focuses on reviewing the literature related to Micro and Small Enterprises and its determinants of sustainability. The primary aim of this literature review is to analyze what has been theoretically said and empirically researched in relation to the topic under study. It begins with a definition of a few key terms used in the study, which will provide profound insight into the topic and facilitate the interpretation of the findings. It comprises a critical review of past studies and conceptual framework.

2.2 What is Micro and Small Enterprise?

There is no universal model for a legal definition of the terms “micro and small enterprises worldwide”. Different countries' laws and regulations give different definitions, depending on their economic development and number of employees. Each country tends to derive its own definition based on the purpose of Micro and small-scale enterprises, which are expected to play in the economy and the programme of assistance designed to achieve that goal. Differences of definitions among countries may arise from differences in level of countries' economic development. According to the International Labor Organization (ILO), (2005), over 50 definitions were identified in 75 different countries. The absence of a uniform definition of MSEs has created a difficulty to have a common understanding. With this regard, (Tegegne Gebre-Egziabher & Meheret Ayenew et al. 2010), reported that, the absence of a single or globally applicable definition has made the task of counting the number of MSEs and assessing their impact extremely difficult across countries. The United Nations Industrial Development Organization gives an alternative definition for the developing countries and defines micro enterprises as business firms with less than 5 employees and small enterprises as business firms with 5-19 employees (UNIDO, 2002). In the USA and Europe, MSE is defined on the basis of number of employees and turnover. The European Commission and Organization for Economic Cooperation and Development defines MSE as having below 250 employees (Habtamu, 2010). In developing countries, the definition is a little bit different from developed nations. For instance, in Tanzania to be an MSE, the major variables are level of employment and capital investment; in Zambia, annual revenue and capital investment are

major requirement. Likewise, the definition given to MSE in Ethiopia includes the variables such as employment, capital investment, production capacity, level of technology and sub sector (World Bank, 2010). Even within the same country, The Definitions also change over time, owing to modifications in price levels, advances in technology or other conditions.

2.2.1 Definition of Micro and Small Enterprises in different countries

Each country give definition to the micro and small enterprises based on its own purpose of micro small enterprises which are expected to play in the economy and the programme of assistance designed to achieve that goal. Varying definitions among countries may arise from differences in industrial organization at different levels of economic development in parts of the country.

Table 2.1: Different definition of micro and small enterprise in different ways.

Categories	Micro enterprise	Small enterprise
European Commission	The average number of employees < 10; Annual turnover < 2 million Euros or Total balance sheet < 2 million Euros;	The average number of employees < 50; Annual turnover < 10 million Euros; or Total balance sheet < 10 million Euros;
World Bank	Less than 10 employees; <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Annual turnover < 100.000 dollars • Total balance sheet < 100.000dollars 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Less than 50 employees; • Annual turnover < 3 million dollars • Total balance sheet < 3 million dollars
Kenya	Less than 10 people Not exceeding Ksh. 500,000	More than 10 but less than 50 Between Ksh. 500,000 to Ksh. 5M

Source: Yodit (2015)

MSEs in Ethiopia are defined by different regional states differently depending on their objective, initial capital and required manpower as a level of the enterprise. Accordingly, the following table set the definition of micro and small enterprise in Ethiopia.

Table 2.2: MSE definition in Ethiopia

Sector	Microenterprise	Small enterprise
Industry	Not more than 10 members/ ≤ 10 / $\leq 600,000$ birr	Between 11 - 50 employees From 600,001-10,000,000 birr
Service	Not more than 10 members/ ≤ 10 / $\leq 400,000$ birr	Between 11 - 50 employees From 400,001-5,000,000 birr
Agriculture	Not more than 10 members/ ≤ 10 / $\leq 400,000$ birr	Between 11 - 50 employees From 400,001-5,000,00 birr

Source: ANRS Work and Training bureau (2023)

2.3 The Micro and Small Enterprise Development Strategy

Designing and implementing appropriate economic policies, strategies, and legal and regulatory framework are prerequisites for creating an enabling environment to promote MSEs. In the federal democratic republic of Ethiopia it could be argued that MSEs development and promotion effort was relatively a recent activity. The new MSE Strategy (2011) included fresh band of target groups, the graduates, (in addition to its classical emphasis on the poor and less skilled people) to form cooperatives and create their own jobs. Besides to creating jobs to the people, the establishments of the enterprises also aimed to bring about technological transfer and new corporate management skills to the nation. In this strategy also new set of areas are identified as requiring attention and priority from the government Mesfin Seyum, (2015). The strategy stresses that “various policy, structural and institutional related problems and bottlenecks” have constrained the role of the MSE sector in and contribution to the national economy. It thus primarily aims at creating enabling legal, institutional and other supportive environments for the development of MSEs. The specific objectives of the strategy include: facilitating economic growth and bring about equitable development; creating long-term jobs; strengthening cooperation between MSEs; providing the basis for medium and large scale enterprises; promoting exports; and balancing preferential treatment between MSE and bigger enterprises. The intended MSE support include creating legal framework; improving access to finance; introducing

different incentive schemes; encouraging partnerships; providing training in entrepreneurship, skills, and management; improving access to appropriate technology, information, advice and markets; and developing infrastructure. The strategy also states its intention to strengthen private sector associations and chambers. A number of institutions are expected to be involved in providing support to the MSEs. The industrial development strategy, issued in 2003, recognizes the promotion of MSEs as an important instrument to create productive private sector and entrepreneurship, hence accords it due emphasis and priority. It promises to make every effort to support this sector through provision of infrastructure (working premises and land), financial facilities, supply of raw materials, training, etc. Federal and regional governments are expected to coordinate the support services. Taken at face value, it would appear that these measures would go a long way in promoting MSEs in the country. However, a study by the ECA (2001) concluded that countries such as Cameron, Ethiopia, Gabon, Nigeria, Senegal and Uganda have shown that the policy environment in which MSEs operate proves to be a major handicap for their expansion and growth. The same study reveals that the complexity of the customs system and the many forms and declarations required have had a negative impact on the general business climate, diverting entrepreneurs' efforts from more productive tasks. The tax levied on imported raw materials is often higher than that on imported finished products that use the same raw materials. The result is a substantial increase in the production cost of MSE operators that require highly taxed imported inputs, thereby limiting their competitiveness.

2.4 Empirical Review

The argument that, some studies Atieno, 2009; Habtamu ., (2012) revealed growth of MSEs affected by internal firm related factors like linkage, network, lack of Searching new opportunities, lack of Preparation of business plan, lack Of Persistence in problem solving and competition and external factors like access to finance, marketing, infrastructure and government regulations. Moreover, small businesses in Africa are crucial in the role they play in an employment creation and general contribution to economic growth is not new. The study made by SubrahmanyaBala, (2011), has probed the impact of globalization on the exports potentials of the small enterprises. According to Stephen and Wasiu (2013), the transformation of traditional industries is one of the contributions of small scale industries to the growth and development of the country. The research undertaken in Tanzania by surveying 160 micro enterprises showed that high tax rates, corruption, and regulation in the form of licenses and permits, are found to be the most important constraints to business operations of micro enterprises Mulugeta, (2011).

The research conducted by Woldegebriel Mezigebe (2012), reported that, one of the major problems found to have been facing MSEs in Addis Ababa is Lack of implementation of appropriate marketing practice has been a very serious setback to MSEs. The most important challenges limited the sustainability of MSEs reported by Woldegebriel Mezigebe (2012), lack business plan, lack of formal and informal association, lack of favorable business environment, high cost and shortage of raw materials, lack of proper institutional support, lack of proper marketing practice, and stiff competition among MSEs in the same business line and medium and large companies. According to the study of Mulugeta(2011),the critical problems of MSEs has recognized and classified in to market-related problems, which are caused by poor market linkage and poor promotional efforts; institution-related problems including bureaucratic bottlenecks, weak institutional capacity, lack of awareness, failure to abide policies, regulations, rules, directives, absence of training ,lack of provision of business development service, and poor monitoring and follow-up; firms-related shortcomings like developing a dependency tradition, extravagant and wasting behavior, and lack of vision and commitment from the side of the operators; MSE-related challenges including lack of selling place, weak accounting and record keeping, lack of experience sharing, and lack of cooperation within and among the MSEs and finally society-related problems such as its distorted attitude about the operators themselves and their products. In addition to the above study, Workbench Fisehal (2007) in his study entitled Constraints of Micro and Small Enterprise in addressing employment opportunity found that MSEs operators in Addis Ababa face lack of adequate training, unfavorable regulatory policy of the government institutions, problem of premise, and inadequate training in the area of marketing and bookkeeping affect the performance and contribution of the sector.

2.5 The Role of Micro and Small Enterprises in Poverty Reduction

Poverty in Ethiopia is widespread and remains a major challenge of sustainable development and stability (Lutheran World Federation of Ethiopia, 2006 cited in Eshetu & Mammo, 2009:2). By now, it is clear and agreeable that poverty, both in urban and/ or rural areas, is all about lack of basic needs, low or inadequate level of income and consumption, poor command over resources, and high level of social exclusion, inequality and vulnerability. In regards to the role of MSEs to economic growth and poverty reduction, still there is no consensus among different writers. Still the two polarized thoughts are vividly seen in different literatures Agyapong, (2010), Anderson et al., 1994, and Staley and Morse, 1965) cited by Martha Workineh (2006). The role played by MSEs, through the various socioeconomic benefits emanating from the sector was found to be eminent in the overall development effort and

process of nations. Research carried out by Biggs (2002) cited in Tegegne Gebre- Egziabiher et al.,(2010) strongly question the role played by MSEs to minimize the incidence of high level poverty in most developing economies through employment creation, income generation and multiplier effects on other sectors of the economy. But nowadays the contribution of micro and small enterprises (MSEs) to employment, growth and sustainable development is widely acknowledged. MSEs are recognized as important vehicles of economic diversification, income generation and distribution, and accelerating the economy of a country. They also help to achieve fair distribution from the incomes of economic growth and thereby help to alleviate some of the problems associated with unequal income distribution. Furthermore, there is no doubt that MSEs have already become major features of the economic fabrics in most developing countries including Ethiopia Martha (Workineh,2006)

According to Siyum Menda (2015), report, 235(72.8%) respondents agreed that, employment creation of MSEs improved their living conditions and 313(96.9%) of the respondents saving habits were improved. Hussmans Ralf et al., (2005), also reported that, MSEs can spark of socioeconomic revival as they need little capital to operate but can contribute much for they work with minimum simple and inexpensive equipment's and management skills. Roy and Wheeler, (2006), indicated that MSE provide a substantial source of employment, thereby contributing to get rid of poverty to the urban poor. The main reason for the urban poor to be absorbed in the MSE is due to the fact that the formal sector does not have the capacity to absorb this growing demand for jobs, and for this reason many have had to look for alternative means to generate a livelihood Roy and Wheeler, (2006).

2.6 The role of micro and small enterprises in economic development

Besides to the job creation and poverty reduction, Micro and small enterprises play an important role in economic development of a country. The enterprises utilize local raw materials that helps to exploit local resources to supply to the market. They are a stepping stone for expansion of industries that help to employment generation. Since they utilize agricultural outputs and other raw materials they link urban rural activities and help for encouragement of rural development. They help for mobilization of local savings. Linkages with bigger industries, provision of regional balance by spreading investments more evenly.

Moreover, Entrepreneurial activities not only enhance national productivity and generate employment, but also help to develop economic independence, as well as strengthen personal and social capabilities among rural communities (S.Jegadeeswari, 2020). Furthermore, SMEs are generally regarded as the

engine of economic performance and equitable development in developing economies. They are labor-intensive, capital-saving, and capable of helping create most of the one billion new jobs the world will need by the end of the century Ethiopia's MSED Policy & Strategy, 2016). SMEs often offer specialized services or products more efficiently, as opposed to larger companies (Felix, et.al 2014).

2.7 Micro and Small Enterprises (MSEs) and their potential contributions to SDGs

Even if there still lacks a universally accepted definition, Micro and Small Enterprises (MSEs) are widely recognized for the important contributions they make to sustainable development, in terms of contributions to economic growth, creation of jobs, provision of public goods and services, as well as poverty alleviation and reduced inequality. MSEs comprise a major share of total private sector entities in both developed and developing countries. According to a recent research finding by OECD, MSEs contributed to 53% and 86% of employment in OECD countries such as the UK and Greece in 2017. In developing countries such as Peru, 98% of private enterprises are MSEs, contributing to 42% of GDP and accounting for 60% of employment. Likewise, MSEs provide about 50% and 80% of employment in Cambodia and Kenya. The critical contribution of MSEs to broader social economic objectives, including job creation makes them a key priority area for achieving the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs). Job creation through MSEs will often directly benefit the poor and vulnerable, particularly women and youth, thereby directly reducing poverty, increasing income and positively impacting on household investments in education and halt over time. MSE development has the potential for wide reaching impacts on the SDGs globally, including SDG 1 (end poverty), SDG 2 (zero hunger), SDG 3 (good health and well-being), SDG 5 (gender equality), SDG 8 (promote inclusive and sustainable economic growth, employment and decent work), and SDG 9 (improve sustainable industrialization and fostering innovation).

2.8 Micro and Small Enterprises Sustainability

There are different point of views in the existing literature on how to measure micro and small enterprises sustainability, and researchers have used a variety of different measures. As Fisseha (2014) cited on his research that, the sustainability measures include, for example, growth of sales, assets, profit, equity, expansion of market share, and continuity with the business for a long time and others (Davidsson & Wiklund, 2000). Moreover, the time span over which growth analyzed in the literature varies considerably, ranging from one to several years. In addition, sustainability has not been measured in absolute or relative terms because of the enterprises perception and goals that they

established. Perhaps the most common means of operationalizing enterprises sustainability is through relatively objective and measurable characteristics such as growth in sales, total assets and profitability. These measures are relatively uncontroversial (methodologically) and data tend to be easily available, increasing the scope for cross study comparability (Freel & Robson, 2004). In this study, profitability and expansion in market share were used as measurement of sustainability of MSEs. This is primarily because of that micro and small enterprises are mainly focused on profitability and expanding market share and these measures are widely adopted by many researchers to measure the dependent variable. The independent variables are management, work related, political legal, marketing, technological and financial variables.

2.9 Determinants for the Sustainability of Micro and Small Enterprises

In Ethiopia, many empirical studies have been conducted to investigate the determinant factors affecting MSEs' growth. Selamawit (2016), conducted Empirical Evidence from the Eastern Zone, Tigray Region, conferring to the research likelihood of enterprises' growth to be engaged in the service sector, capital accumulation of an enterprise, and educational level of employees of an enterprise. Contrarily, the age and size of an enterprise were found to have negative and significant effects on enterprises' likelihood of growing. The study conducted by (Yitbarek, 2016) finds a positive and significant relationship between firm growth and external factors such as access to credit, working spaces, and marketing premises as well as human capital factors including entrepreneur's education, business skills, and training. The finding supports the research hypotheses, which possess that these factors have a direct linkage with firm growth. Similarly, findings show that firm growth and firm age are initially inversely related but this negative relationship stays only for some time since as firm age increases, firms start to grow and become sustainable and the relationship becomes positive towards the end.

Generally ,these previous studies classified the determinant factors into Entrepreneurial characteristics such as owner/operator gender, age, education level, previous work experience, management skill, economic background, and marital status, firms related factors including age, size, initial capital, location, formality, type of business and external factors such as access to credit, infrastructure, market, working place, technology, social services, and other legal and regulatory frame works.

But currently, the determinant factors for micro and small enterprises sustainability may differ from place to place and from time to time. Based on this the researcher identified the determinants on the following ways;

2.9.1. Internal Factors

The internal environment includes factors in the business environment that are largely controllable by the business Fatoki & Garwe.(2010).

2.9.1.1 Management Factors

Among many Management factors (management skill, experience and strategic business planning) have been mentioned in many studies in link with MSEs Growth and survival. A study conducted by beza(2022) mentioned that, Irrespective of the size of any business large micro or small, management or management inabilities are Owners/managers' age, education level, lack of prior experience in accounting and business management, family size, MSE's age, lack of business knowledge, lack of strongly held confidence and underdeveloped entrepreneurial mindsets/entrepreneurship competency among the operators of MSEs, lack of good communication skill and lack of technical and managerial experience/skill gap all influenced the sustainability and growth of MSEs in Ethiopia (Alene, 2020; EEA, 2015; Ethiopia's MSED Policy & Strategy, 2016; MSED Strategy, 2011). MSE growth is poorly correlated with the owner's age and family size. This suggests that the younger the owner with a smaller family grows faster than the older the owner with a larger family. This result confirmed that the youngest owners' enterprises were more successful than the other group (Kassa, 2021). The owner education and prior experience has also a positive and considerable impact on MSE growth. This shows that MSEs owned by people with a greater degree of education and prior experience expand quicker than their peers (Alene, 2020). Most of the enterprise owners did not have prior experience in basic accounting and business management and thus they are unable to effectively and efficiently manage their businesses. This invariably resulted in large scale start up failures and loss of hope, even desperation, on the part of the operators (Ethiopia's MSED Policy & Strategy, 2016; MSED Strategy, 2011). Furthermore, owners and employees job-related factors such as a lack of harmonious relationships among employees/teamwork, lack of initiative to assess one's strength, and lack of tolerance to work hard or motivation are the primary internal variables that affect MSEs sustainability and growth in Ethiopia (Ethiopia's MSED Policy & Strategy, 2016; Rahel, 2018). In the contemporary global dynamic business environment strategically thinking and systematically decision-making are

also important for small enterprises growth and survival Dobbs & Hamilton, (2007). Business strategies refer to an internal management action changing the firm plan premeditated to cope with external environment changes in order to achieve the firm's business objectives Blackbur,(2013). A business strategy incorporates various major functional strategies, namely; marketing, financial management, human capital and information system (Kotler& Armstrong, 1999). So, the firm's probability of survival and growth is highly depending on the ability of a business to plan and excited realistic strategy based on its resources Fadahunsi, (2012).

2.9.2. External Factors

Factors such as economic variables and markets; crime and corruption, financial, technological, labor, work related/ infrastructure/ and regulations make up the external environment Fatoki&Garwe, (2010).

2.9.2.1 Financial factors

Among from external factors financial factors can be considered both internal and external factor. Many researches have been discussed that small and starting up enterprise are influenced by financial constraints than large and medium enterprises. As beza(2022) cited on his research that financial factors of micro and small enterprises sustainability are lack of access to finance, poor book keeping and accounting system, shortage of adequate initial investment, shortage of working capital, poor repayment culture and their inappropriate use of credit are the major financial factors that determine the sustainability and growth of MSEs in Ethiopia (Addis, 2019; Alene, 2020; Ethiopia's MSED Policy & Strategy, 2016;According to Abdel, Rowena & Robyn (2010), small business owner-managers have very basic understanding of financial and accounting information and have serious problems with financial planning literacy. Ademola& Michael also identified key challenges of MSEs among them poor accounting method and practices have been mentioned Ademola& Michael, (2012). Furthermore, according to (Beck, 2006) cited in ElSaid, (2013), small firms consistently report more financing obstacles than medium and large enterprises According to Variyam and Kraybill, (1994), although programmer for assisting small businesses have been implemented in many Sub-Saharan African countries through cooperative services, microfinance institutions, business planning, product and market development, and the adoption of technology, the programs have failed to realize sustained growth and development in small enterprises. This is caused through small-sized enterprises are exposed to quite bankruptcy arising from problems related to business and managerial skills, access to finance and macroeconomic policy of a nation and it creates liquidation. Because of this Small

businesses face a greater difficulty in obtaining credit than micro businesses, which typically have access to microfinance institutions (MFIs') because their lending needs are within the capacity of MFIs'. Due to the burdensome bureaucracy and high collateral requirements of the microfinance institutions, a huge number of micro and small businesses have not applied for a loan or credit from formal financial institutions. As a result, most MSEs prefer to use personal savings and contributions from relatives as a main source of credit (MSED Strategy, 2011; Kassa, 2021;). Besides to collateral and bureaucracy constraints, most enterprises are unable to obtain finance/credit at the right time and of the required amount. Furthermore, due to management inefficiency, poor repayment culture, inappropriate use of credit, lack of experience in using credit to improve competitiveness, and lack of precise information needed to assess the risk of providing money to MSEs, Commercial banks and formal money lending organizations are hesitant to lend money to MSEs or request strict requirements such as collateral security. Enterprises having access to finance expand faster than those with limited credit, despite the fact that the majority of businesses encounter numerous problems in obtaining debt financing from formal institutions (Kassa, 2021; Meressa, 2020).

2.9.2.2 Political legal factors

In case of political and legal factors Many MSEs fail in spite of support from government and private initiatives that support and develop small businesses. Political-legal variables such as lack of government support, lack of awareness creation, tax and lack of accessible information on government regulations are the major political and legal factors that determine the sustainability and growth of MSEs in Ethiopia (beza, 2022). Although the Ethiopian government has attempted to liberalize and improve the policy, regulatory, and institutional support environment for MSEs, resulting in increased investment and competition as well as improvements in licensing procedures, Furthermore, weak business environment, and policy and regulatory barriers are among the common challenges' MSEs are facing in Ethiopia (Solomon, et al., 2016). Currently enterprises products and services fail to sell and to make market linkage due to political instability in Ethiopia and in the Amhara region. Inflation in construction materials lead the enterprises to fail. Political instability cases a budget shortage that affect them to get credit.

2.9.2.3 Technological factors

Technological constraints also reviled in many studies as driving factor of MSEs failure. In a competitive business environment the role of information technology (IT) and internet is significant in the process of providing effectively efficient services, products, and packages to achieve a competitive advantage over competitors Hassen and Svensson, (2014). AlShaikh, (1998) gave an insight on why infrastructural problem is high in developing countries than developed countries. He noted that the technological environment and the infrastructure of developing countries are still lagging behind the developed Countries, probably because the developed nations produce the technology, while the developing nations import it. He further emphasized that even though globalization seems to make the importation of such technology less cumbersome, most MSEs in these developing countries still lack the finance where to acquire the technology. To solve technological problems and their operational and competitiveness difficulties, MSEs must first commit for change and needs continual improvement (Ethiopia's MSED Policy & Strategy, 2016; MSED Strategy, 2011). Technology encourage the innovation for the entrepreneur to introduce a new business idea for improved products, new production processes, new markets and marketing/sales methods, new distribution channels and promotion, new raw materials, improved services, new methods of financing, new technology and many others. . Ollo-Lopez and Aramendia-Muneta, (2012) indicated that by adopting technology a business has a positive influence on productivity, directly or indirectly and there is great potential for a sustainable development. For example the use of social media network, e-mail and e-commerce and can significantly reduce for example transport costs incurred since advertising, sending mail, banking and buying goods is much easier (Manochehri, Al-Esmail & Ashrafi, 2012).

2.9.2.4 Marketing factors

Marketing functions are important for the promotion, growth and development of MSEs. As beza (2022) cited on his research that marketing factors of micro and small enterprises sustainability are inadequacy of market, difficulty of searching new market, lack of demand forecasting, poor customer handling system, lack of available market information, lack of promotion, lack of connection with successful and other businesses or market linkage, and lack of adaptability are the major marketing factors that determine the sustainability of MSEs in Ethiopia. Empirical results indicated a positive relationship between MSEs growth and market access (Addis, 2019; Amare, 2020; Ethiopia's MSED Policy & Strategy, 2016; Gemechu & Teklemariam, 2016; Gebrehiwot and Wolday, 2006; Hagos et al., 2014; Kassa. When we see the impact of market linkage, businesses that have a stronger connection to

a variety of organizations they provide their services/products faster than their competitors; which is in line with the market access theory of change (Meressa, 2020;). He also demonstrated that businesses with more connections to diverse organizations through trade fairs and bazaars grow quicker than their competitors. In general; MSEs which had access to market linkage registered higher growth rate than those which had no access to market linkage (Alemayehu and Gecho, 2016). Lack of market linkage and poor promotion and awareness creation system, on the other hand, makes MSEs', particularly small businesses, not benefited from technology transfers, marketing their products and other useful business relationships (Tarfasa et al., 2016).

2.9.2.5 Work related/infrastructure/ factors

Work related/infrastructural/ factors are the basic government structures that hinders enterprises to their sustainability. In the study of Beza Muche(2022) regarding work related factors such as electricity, lack of access to land or work place/shade and inappropriate business location are the main challenges that affect the sustainability and growth of MSEs in Ethiopia. The empirical findings of most previous studies revealed that access to infrastructure is a crucial determinant in MSEs success, since those with sufficient infrastructure expand quicker than those that do not (Amare, 2020; Batisa, 2019; EEA, 2015; Gemechu & Teklemariam, 2016; Gebremariam, 2017). Enterprises that have adequate land as a working premise have a better chance of making a profitable and grow faster than their competitors (Alene, 2020; Meressa, 2020). Furthermore, MSEs that are operating at their own working premise grow faster than those that operates at rented and at family working premise. This implies that, MSEs having better access to adequate infrastructure expand quicker than their competitors. As a result, access to infrastructure (such as access to working premises, proximity to raw materials and having enabling working environments) has a positive and considerable impact on MSE sustainability and growth (EEA, 2015; Hagos et al., 2014). On the other side, poor business environment and lack of adequate infrastructure (like frequent electric power outages, and a scarcity of water) have significant negative impact on MSEs sustainability and growth (Alemayehu and Gecho, 2016; Tarfasa et al., 2016). Similarly, most of the MSEs are working at a very small room which is completely unsuitable for production and service delivery (Feyisa & Tamene, 2019). Business location has also significant impact on the growth of MSEs. Micro and Small enterprises located near to different infrastructures grow faster than enterprises far from different services and infrastructures (Addis, 2019; Meressa, 2020).

2.10 Conceptual Framework

Based on the above review of literature, the researcher adopts Conceptual framework. According to Mugenda and Mugenda (2003) conceptual framework is a diagrammatic presentation of the relationship between dependent and independent variables. These selected factors have been used frequently by previous literatures and supposed to be the critical success factors of MSEs. Sustainability of enterprises in Sinan Woreda administration depends on certain factors as set out into two categories as dependent and independent variables. In this study, the dependent variable is sustainability of MSEs while independent variables are Work related factors, management factors, financial factor, technological factor, Marketing factor and political factors as presented in figure 1

Figure 2.1 Conceptual frameworks

Source: developed by the investigator from different literatures /2023

2.11 Research Hypothesis

The researcher will apply hypothesis testing instruments. This is in order to predict the casual effect of variables and to determine the probability of a specific true hypothesis.

Hypothesis1. Work related factor has a positive and significant effect on Micro and Small Enterprise sustainability.

Hypothesis2. Management Factors has a positive and significant effect on Micro and Small Enterprise sustainability.

Hypothesis3. Technological Factor has positive and significant influence on Micro and Small Enterprise sustainability.

Hypothesis4. Financial Factor has positive and significant influence on Micro and Small Enterprise sustainability.

Hypothesis5. Marketing Factor has a positive and significant effect on Micro and Small Enterprise sustainability.

Hypothesis6. Political Factor has positive and significant influence on Micro and Small Enterprise sustainability.

CHAPTER THREE

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

3.1 Introduction

Research methodology is a way to systematically solve the research problem. It may be understood as a science of studying how research is done scientifically (Kothari,2004). This part of the paper deals with the overall research methodology that the researcher will be followed during in conducting the entire study. That is, the overall approach in which the researcher will guide to study the identified research problem. Accordingly, it contains the description of the study area, research approach, model and model specification, sampling procedure, data collection and analysis techniques.

3.2 Research Design

Research design is a master plan specifying the methods and procedures for collecting and analyzing the required information (Kothari, 2004).

Therefore, the research design serves as guide for data generation in order to conduct effective research with in a limit resource and to address the determinants of micro and small enterprises sustainability descriptive and explanatory method is the most appropriate method. The descriptive method is special importance for this particular study to assess determinants of sustainability of MSEs. The method descriptive research design is special importance for this particular study to portray how the micro and small enterprise business activities determined by several variables such as, financial, technology, marketing, work related, political and management factor. The study employs explanatory in that the relationship between variables is correlated with an aim of estimating the integrated influence of the factors on sustainability. The prime goal of explanatory research design is to determine how events occur and which ones may influence specific outcomes. It also helps the researcher in planning and implementing the study in a way that will allow the researcher to obtain the desired results, increasing the chances of obtaining information that can be associated with the real situation (Myers et al. 2013). To collect the data from the respondents a structured questionnaire and semi-structured interview

survey technique will be conducted. The research findings, conclusions, and recommendations will be briefly discussed based on the result.

3.3 Research Approach

There are two kinds of research approaches which are quantitative and qualitative. Understanding of both approaches is important to choose the appropriate research approach and to increase the efficiency of the study. These two approaches are extensively used in business and management research. The research under consideration was carried out using a mixed research approach; the rationale for combining both quantitative and qualitative approach is to better understand the research problem by combining both numerical values from quantitative research and the detail of qualitative research, as well as to neutralize the limitations of using either approach alone. According to Creswell (2009), the mixed research approach employs to compensate for the shortcomings of one method with the strengths of the other. Hence for this specific study the researcher will be using both combinations of quantitative and qualitative approaches.

The quantitative and qualitative mixed research is preferred in order to increase the validity and reliability credibility of the result in the research. Since the use of mixed approach ensure that biases inherent in either method are neutralized by the strength of others. Bryman & Bell (2003), suggest that the combination of methods emerges as the most valid and reliable way to develop understanding of complex social reality. Thus, using the combination of both methods enables the researcher to collect adequate, relevant and reliable data which improve the validity and reliability of the study.

3.4 Data Source

The study relies on both primary and secondary data sources. The researcher used primary data from those which are collected afresh and for the first time, and thus happen to be original in character. The secondary data, on the other hand, are those which have already been collected by someone else and which have already been passed through the statistical process (Kothari, 2004). The primary data will be collected through questionnaire and interview. Secondary data of manuals, reports, past research works, journals and internets were used as a supportive document for reference.

3.5 Target Population

The total population and target population of this study are the existing registered and legalized MSEs in the study area, and which consists of 689 enterprises.

3.6 Sample Size Determination

The study grouped the population into strata. From each stratum, the study is used simple random sampling to select the respondents. Based on Yamane Taylor, (1967),

To determine the sample size for the study, the researcher used the following a simplified formula. Sample size for the study is determined using the formula described below as stated used by Israel G.P. (1992) and used by Olouch (2012).
$$n = \frac{N}{1 + N(e)^2}$$

Where: n = sample size; N = size of population; and e = precision level

N - is the population size of the Micro and Small Enterprises in the study area,

e - is the sampling error or the precision level, which is 5 % for this study because of its 95% confident level

$n = \frac{N}{1 + N(e)^2} = \frac{689}{1 + 689(0.05)^2} = 253$ Micro and Small Enterprises respondents will be select by simple random sampling depend on the above formula.

Finally from woreda work and training office 2 head offices, 4 team leaders and 6 experts will be select purposively because the participants are leaders and future leaders these positions are assumed to be major source of information for the data gathering of the study.

The researcher to select sample from each Association sample proportionate will be use. According to the above idea the population and sample taken from each Association is shown in the table.

The procedure of selecting sample respondent is indicated by the table below.

Table 3.1: Sample of the Respondents

S/N	MSEs dep't	Total population	participants in the sample respondents	Headoffice,Team Leaders/Experts	Total Respondent
1	Manufacturing	137	51		
2	Construction	75	27		
3	Urban agriculture	207	76		
4	Service	150	55		
5	Trade	120	44		
	Total	689	253	12	265

Source: Sinan Woreda Administration work and training office, 2023.

3.7 Sampling Technique

In order to obtain essential information, the researcher will use Stratified random sampling technique. Stratified random sampling technique used for the division of population in to smaller group or in to strata. Stratified random sampling technique used because it is accurate, easily accessible, divisible into relevant strata and it enhances better comparison; hence representation across strata Kothari, (2004). This method was chosen because the technique reduces sample selection bias and therefore ensures that certain segments of the population are not underrepresented or over represented. In the sampling procedure, the enterprises were stratified into five strata that is manufacturing, construction, urban agriculture, trade and services and the sample of each sector was determined by proportional sampling methods. From each stratum, the study applied random sampling technique to select the respondents. In other words, the researcher will use purposive (non probability) sampling to draw samples for head offices, team leaders and experts.

3.8 Data Collection Tools

3.8.1 Questionnaire

Questionnaires are written forms that are asked exact questions of all individuals in the sample group, and which respondents can answer at their own convenience (Gall et al., 2007). The data provided by questionnaires can be more easily analyzed and interpreted than the data obtained from verbal responses. Questionnaires are supposed to be better to get a great amount of data from a large number of respondents in a relatively shorter time with the smallest quantity of cost.

According to Jonathan Law (2016), a questionnaire can take Likert scale question form; A Likert scale is a question which contains 5 or 7 response options. The choices range from Strongly Agree to Strongly Disagree so the survey maker can get a holistic view of people's opinions and their level of agreement but the respondent can state their additional feelings in advance, not during questioning.

In order to obtain the intended data from the respondents the researcher will be prepared and distribute open ended questionnaires to 253 respondents. The questionnaires will be prepare in English language and then translate to Amharic. Then the two versions will be evaluated for linguistic by language experts. It is use to solve certain inconveniences and communication barriers that will happen on the respondents in some cases because of language.

Testing for reliability is important as it refers to the consistency across the parts of a measuring instrument (Huck, 2007). According to Kothari, 2004 to ensure validity and reliability of questionnaires pilot survey testing is advisable. In order to measure internal consistency of the questionnaire the most commonly used measure is the Cronbach Alpha coefficient. It is viewed as the most appropriate measure of reliability when making use of Likert scales (Whitley, 2002, Robinson, 2009). Hinton et al. (2004) have suggested four cut-off points for reliability, which includes excellent reliability (0.90 and above), high reliability (0.70-0.90), moderate reliability (0.50-0.70) and low reliability (0.50 and below) (Hinton et al., 2004). In order to test reliability and validity of questionnaires the researcher were prepared and distribute close ended questionnaires for 30 sample respondents. From 30 distributed questionnaires all were analyzed giving a response rate of 100%. The researcher were analyzed this questionnaire reliability and validity through SPSS.

Table3.2 Pilot test of questionnaire reliability

Reliability Statistics			
Factors	Cronbach's Alpha	N of questions	Sample size
Management factor (MG)	0.978	6	30
Financial factor (FC)	0.888	4	30
Technological factor(TG)	0.895	2	30
Work related factor(WR)	0.969	3	30
Political factor (PL)	0.930	2	30
Marketing factor(MK)	0.961	4	30

Sources: output result SPSS

According to the SPSS output result the Cronbach's Alpha score of MG, FC, MK , WR, TG and PL were 0.978, 0.969, 0.961, 0.930, 0.888 and 0.895 respectively which is excellent and the questions are internally consistency (reliable). Because Cronbach Alpha is a reliability coefficient that indicates how well the questionnaires are positively correlated to one another. The closer Cronbach Alpha is 1, the high internal consistency.

Even though reliability is important for research study, it is not sufficient unless combined with validity. In other words, for a test to be reliable, it also needs to be valid (Wilson, 2010). The validity of questionnaires was tested through the Pearson correlation coefficient i.e. the obtained correlation coefficient against the critical value based on the total survey respondent (N), the critical value of Pearson correlation coefficient at 0.05 level of significant is 0.349 and at p-value of 0.000 significant level the obtained correlation coefficient value on SPSS output result of the questionnaire is greater than 0.349 highly significant. So it was a valid question.

3.8.2. Interview

Creswell (2009), states that semi-structured interviews can be used when researchers record and transcribe responses as per written interview guidelines. Accordingly, the study used a written guidance interview guideline. In this study, semi-structured interviews were the main instruments of data collection for the qualitative data collection methodology. Semi-structured interview will be used to collect data from the head offices and the team leaders and senior experts of 12 interviewees.

3.9 Data Analysis Technique

The Data will be analyzed with the help of Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS Version 23) program through a descriptive statistics to provide details concerning on the determinates that affect the sustainability of Micro and Small Enterprises. Data from questionnaires will summarized, edited, coded, tabulated and analyzed through SPSS.

3.10 Variable Specification

This study has only a single dependent variable that is Micro and Small Enterprises sustainability (VS) and more than one independent variable that could contribute to determine the extent of the dependent variable. According to the literature reviewed, there are six factors that determine the Micro and Small Enterprises sustainability. The following table shows the operational definition of the independent variables.

Table3.3 Description of Variables

Determinants	Symbols	Description	Measurements systems
Marketing	MK	Marketing factors	Customer handling system, market information, promotion and awareness creation, market linkage
Technology	TG	Technological factors	Availability of IT, internet, machinery and equipment
Finance	FC	Financial factors	Access to finance, book keeping and accounting system, use of credit, working capital
Work related	WR	Work related factors	Accessibility of electricity and water, working and selling place, business location
Management	MG	Management factors	Strategic business plan, managers education level, division of duties and responsibilities, management skill, teamwork and family size of the enterprise
Political	PT	Political-legal factors	Government support and Accessibility of government regulations

3.11 Modeling and model specification

When there are two or more than two independent variables, the analysis concerning relationship is known as multiple correlations and the equation describing such relationship as the multiple regression equation. Multiple regression equation assumes the form $Y = \alpha + \beta_1 X_1 + \beta_2 X_2 + \dots + e$ (C.R. Kothari 1995). Therefore, in order to determine the extent of the dependent variable the researcher will use the following multiple regression equation.

Where, Y_i = is the dependent variable

α = is the interception of the regression model

$\beta_1, \beta_2, \beta_i$ = is coefficient for each independent variable

x_1, x_2, x_i = is independent variable

ϵ_i = is an error term.

So that the researcher equation is:

$$SMSE = \alpha + \beta_1 MK + \beta_2 TG + \beta_3 FC + \beta_4 WR + \beta_5 MG + \beta_6 PT + \epsilon$$

3.12 Ethical Consideration

According to Leedy and Ormrod, (2013), in doing any research, there is an ethical responsibility to do the work honestly and with integrity. The basic principle of ethical research is to preserve and protect the human dignity and rights of all subjects involved in a research project. In this regard, the researcher will be carry out in necessary approval and permission letter from debre markos university and the written permission that will given to the selected organizations based on a letter inquiry make by the researcher throughout the whole process of data collection all the respondents will be treated in an ethical manner with mutual understanding of each other, further more brief introduction will be make about the study and its objectives to the key informants and focus group discussants. Though, in this process the researcher is let the participants know the purpose of the research and participate up on the consent. The questionnaire provided to the respondents have general information about the purpose of the study .In addition to that it is indicate that the respondents need no mention their names in the questionnaire and all the responses are kept confidential.

CHAPTER FOUR

DATA PRESENTATION, INTERPRETATION and DISCUSSION

4.1 Introduction

For achieving the objective of the study (which indicated in chapter 1 of this study), the researcher designed and distributed the questionnaire for the selected sample respondents from Rebu Gebeya Town Micro and Small Enterprises.

Moreover, semi-structure interview conducted with those concerned officials of the Sinan Woreda Administration Work and Training office. As stated in the methodology section, for the method of data collection questionnaires were administered to micro and small enterprises, who are working their activity at present. 253 questionnaires were distributed, from 253 distributed questionnaires 240 question papers are returned and all were analyzed giving a response rate of 94%. 12 office heads, team leaders/experts from the office were used as a source of data through semi-structured interviews. A variety of semi-structured interview questions related to the status and role of Micro and Small Enterprises, the role and performance of government support to the Micro and Small Enterprises, the determinant factors of Micro and Small Enterprises sustainability, and how each determinant affects Micro and Small Enterprises sustainability were delivered.

Hence, in this chapter the collected primaries are presented, interpreted, and discussed through the result of SPSS output with the help of tables, percentage, and graphs. Moreover, for ease of understanding and simplicity the collected data are organized and presented throughout this chapter as follows:

4.2 General Profile of the Respondents

Table4.1 Demographic Characteristics of the Respondents

Variable	Category	Frequency	%
Sex of Respondents	Female	50	20.8
	Male	190	79.2
	Total	240	100
Age of Respondents	18-25	77	32.1

	26-33	112	46.7
	34-51	51	21.2
	Above52	0	0
	Total	240	100
Marital Status	Single	137	57.1
	Married	98	40.8
	Divorced	5	2.1
	Widowed	0	0
	Total	240	100
Educational level	No education	9	3.8
	Grade10/12completed &below	138	57.5
	Diploma	47	19.6
	Degree	31	12.9
	Masters	0	0
	Others	15	6.3
	Total	240	100
Main activity of the enterprise	Manufacturing	51	21.2
	Construction	18	7.5
	Urban agriculture	75	31.3
	Service	52	21.7
	Trade	44	18.3
	Total	240	100
Work experience of the enterprise	5 years &below	177	73.8
	6-10 years	47	19.6
	11-15 years	10	4.2

	16&above	6	2.5
	Total	240	100

Source; survey data, 2023

The above table 4.1 shows among the respondents 190(79.2%) were male whereas females comprise only 50(20.8%). In Ethiopia both females and males are working in micro and small enterprises at different positions as owners, managers or employees. However there was a more male respondent in the study than female and this indicates that majority of the employees who are owner, manager and employees in the micro and small enterprises are males. Regardless of the age distribution among the micro and small enterprises 77(32.1%) were found to be in the age range of 18-25 which is known for its energetic enrolment as a major productive force at different stages of work. On the other hand the majority of the enterprises 112 (46.7%) of the enterprises were found to be in the age category between 26 and 33. Also, 51(21.2%) of the respondent were found to be in the age category between 34 and 51. This shows the majority of respondents are between ages of 26 and 33 years in which they are active and energetic work forces that are ready to act where there is comfortable situation is prepared for them because of they are in adult age and have many responsibilities in the future. Also they are the age group expected to imitate and flexible according to the environment. Concerning the educational background of the enterprises, 9(3.8%) of participants have no education, 138(57.5%) of the participants were grade 10/12 completed and below, 47(19.6%) have college Diploma, 31 (12.9%) have a degree and 15(6.3%) have a qualification of others . The finding shows that most of the respondents had attained a primary and secondary education, college diploma and degree completed. Because of this most of young males and females who have drop out of primary and secondary education and who have completed from college or university came to the woreda and engaged in forming enterprise. And the qualification helped to them to create and imitate new technologies. Regarding the marital status of the respondent, out of the 240 respondents, 137 (57.1%) was found that single, 98 (40.8%) are married and 5 (2.1%) divorced.

Regarding to main activity of the respondents, out of the 240 respondents, 51 (21.3%) were working in manufacturing sector, 18 (7.5%) were working in construction sector, the rest 31.3% and 21.7% , 18.3% of respondents were involved in urban agriculture , service and trade sector respectively.

Figure 4.1 sector respondents engaged in

These shows that in Rebu gebeya town the manufacturing, urban agriculture and service sector were actively working and providing services to the community at different level. concerning on the enterprises work experience, 73.8% of respondents were worked in the enterprise from 5 years and below, 19.6% of respondents were worked in the enterprise from 6-10 years , the rest 4.2% and 2.5% respondents were working in the enterprise from 11-15 and above 15 years respectively. This indicated that respondents have enough experience to accomplish the vision and to be competitive from same enterprises.

4.3 Analysis of Determinants for the sustainability of micro and small Enterprises

Table 4.2 factors related to the management factors of enterprises.

No	MG	Mean	Std.dev
1.	Lack of strategic business planning	1.55	1.141
2.	Lack of clear division of duties and responsibility among employees	1.48	1.027
3.	Poor management skill	1.35	0.897
4.	Lack of harmonious relationships among team work	1.42	1.067
5.	Managers education level on your business	1.44	0.988
6.	Family size of enterprises	1.50	1.019

Source: Survey Data, 2023

On the first item, Regarding Lack of strategic business planning have an influence on the MSEs sustainability. Based on the respondents lack of business planning has a mean value of 1.55 and standard deviation of 1.141. Based on this Lack of strategic business planning have an influence on the MSEs sustainability and it is the main problem in determining the sustainability of the micro and small enterprises. This result supported by sinan worda work and training office extension department. This is occurred due to lack of awareness on the significance of having business plan on their productivity and profitability and they consider that preparing strategic plan spent more time at work.

In different studies indicated, there is a visible influence on having strategic business plan on the growth and sustainability of the enterprises. Admasu abera(2012) have showed that a strategic business plan is the most important aspect for the success of any business venture. Because an entrepreneurial team is necessary to implement the businesses' objectives as outlined in the strategic business plan. The strategic business plan is a framework which a business must operate within. It will ultimately determine whether the business performance is good or bad. For enterprises managers to seek external support, strategic planning is the most important document to achieve future objectives and it is also sales document that they are ever likely help to produce. A good strategic business plan is not only important in developing the opportunity but also essential in determining the resources required, obtaining those resources, and successfully managing the resulting venture. Taking this into consideration, MSEs sector should therefore ensure that they equip their employees with the necessary strategic business plan skills.

With regard to lack of clear division of duties and responsibility among employees the mean value of the respondent is 1.48 and standard deviation of 1.027. This shows that Lack of clear division of duties and responsibility among employees have a better chance to influence the MSEs sustainability. This result helps the employees to be more productive, because of less duplication of efforts and less confusion of works. This result supported by different studies according to JacintaWambui (2014) have showed that teams function most efficiently when members share a common understanding of each other's duties and responsibilities. indeed, one of the reasons why teams fail is lack of clarity among team members regarding their respective duties, responsibilities and expectations they hold of one another when working together to accomplish their vision,mission,goals and objectives. Having this, the enterprises should divide the duties and responsibilities among to the employees in order to help the employees to look beyond their own individual positions and learn to understand, respect and value

the unique contributions of one another, and they recognize that the overall success of the team is a function of shared responsibilities and duties.

On the question item of Poor management skill, the mean value is 1.35 and standard deviation of 0.897. This indicates that Poor management skill have a better effect to sustain the MSEs. Based this if the enterprises manager have poor management skill the employees have no interest to work hard and are not motivated to create new product ideas. Poor management skills can be of the managers personality problems like of poor communication skills, managers single decision making process, delegation of work to the employees, problem solving skills, rewarding and encouraging skills and improper training ways. We have seen people with poor management can decrease the enterprises productivity and employees moral that lead to waste of resources. On the opposite side, a manager with good management skills help the enterprises to facilitate to improve employees efficiency and to be productive. As we have seen it practically, we can give our witness that an enterprises with managers poor management skill have low employees working moral, demotivated employees, decreased productivity, decreased profitability and employee turnover. This cases result in the enterprises failure.

Based on Mizan sibhatu,(2018) Managerial skills are important in guiding the path which an organization is to follow in order to arrive at the designated goal. Entrepreneurs' managers control and acts of the member of the staff and guide them to ensure profitability and they build synergy for the attainment of organizational goals. Good Management skills among SMEs is important as it will influence the manner in which the SMEs operation hence how it is able to interact with the environment. Through better and experienced management, an organization is able to access financial assistance as the financial and other recorded requested by lenders may be easily availed. Management skills are therefore necessary to enable organizational goals to be accomplished through the functions of planning, staffing, directing, controlling activities, coordination and directing. Briefing good management skill leads to great involvement with the micro and small enterprises sustainability that help the employees to create motivation, determination, energy, drive, and an optimistic approach to achieve their goals.

As illustrated in the table, Lack of harmonious relationships among team work the mean value is 1.42 and standard deviation of 1.067 indicates that Lack of harmonious relationships among team work have a better effect on the MSEs sustainability. The questionnaire respondent's response supports this result having harmonious relationship with employees will shape a happy and comfortable work environment where employees are helpful, motivating and supportive to each other. in such an environment, it is

possible for the employees to perform better at their works. As Andualem gezahegn, (2013) argued when you work together as a team, you may form a bond with those closest to you. You might get skills in common or enjoy quality time together. Harmonious relationships among team work enables employees to interact with each other that helps a great learning opportunity for new employees and encourages personal growth, increase job satisfaction and involve respect, communication and honesty.

Regarding managers education level the mean value is 1.44 and standard deviation is 0.988. This result shows that Managers education level have a better role for ensuring the sustainability of micro and small enterprises. Education is a powerful tools for successful business here the researcher's emphasis on formal education. In micro and small business strategy educated entrepreneurs, particularly university graduates have been given priority in allocating credit, land working premises, and other supports. Analyzing the educational level of the entrepreneurs also helps to know the effectiveness of the entrepreneurs. Abraham,Endrias,Zemach (2015) on their research conclude that operators with more education and training were more likely to be successful in the micro and small enterprise sectors, that is the operators with higher education level and experience have greater chance of succeeding than those with-out education and experience. Dagmawit and Yishak (2016) also concludes that Education was found positively and significantly influences the probability of MSEs capital growth at less than 10% significance level Since education level of owners influence capital growth of MSEs. Education levels of owners of MSEs and growth of MSEs have a positive relationship. Hence educated managers helps the employees to guide the activities and enable them to manipulate new technologies easily.

On the six items of Family size of enterprises, From the total respondent the mean value is 1.50 and standard deviation of 1.019. This indicates that Family size of enterprises have a better role to ensure micro and small enterprises sustainability. This result also supported by Alemayehu & Gecho, 2016; Family is a base for youth success and failure. In an experienced family working a business, their youngsters tend to create a new business, and they develop experience on how to operate the business. Entrepreneurial family background is important to identify solutions for challenges and indicating how to survive the business. As Andualem gezahegn, (2013) argued While higher initial number of family size or employment leads to the increment in the mean compound capital growth. Hence in order to have the enterprises sustainability the higher the enterprises family help to produce high and to get satisfactory profit. Generally as illustrated from the table

Table 4.3 factors related to the financial factors of enterprises.

No	FC	Mean	Std.dev
1.	Lack of access to finance	1.62	0.919
2.	Poor Book keeping and accounting system	1.47	0.997
3.	Inappropriate use of credit	1.41	1.201
4.	Shortage of working capital	1.49	1.063

Source: survey data, 2023

Regarding to the above table on the item of lack of access to finance have a mean value of 1.62 and 0.919 standard deviation. This shows lack of finance hinders micro and small enterprises to their expansion, and it is one of the major problem for the enterprises sustainability in the study area.

This result supported by different studies. According to Amadasun and Mutezo,(2022) access to finance significantly affects the competitive growth of micro and small enterprises. Thus, several specific and harmonized financial policy actions are needed in financial market to establish an enabling policy that will ease enterprises access to adequate funding programs. The lack of finance directly influence the growth and sustainability of the enterprises that lead them to be stable in their productivity. According to Beza Muche(2022),Lack of access to medium or long-term loans is a key stumbling block for businesses looking to grow their operations. The reasons for this are well known, particularly the fact that MSEs pose a high risk to lenders because many of them lack adequate assets and are under capitalized. a. Furthermore, due to management inefficiency, poor repayment culture, inappropriate use of credit, lack of experience in using credit to improve competitiveness, and lack of precise information needed to assess the risk of providing money to MSEs, Commercial banks and formal money lending organizations are hesitant to lend money to MSEs or request strict requirements such as collateral security. Enterprises having access to finance expand faster than those with limited credit, despite the fact that the majority of businesses encounter numerous problems in obtaining debt financing from formal institutions (Kassa, 2021; Meressa, 2020).

In item two on the Poor Book keeping and accounting system have an effect on the sustainability of MSEs the mean value is 1.47 and standard deviation of 0.997. Bookkeeping is beneficial to the enterprises in order to effectively manage the enterprises cash flows, and helps to know transactions

that are essential to know profits and or losses. The bookkeeping and accounting system helps the enterprises to plan for the future and being well informed about running of the business. furthermore it does comply with the tax institutions in order to pay corporate tax. This result supported by different studies. According to Negou Ernest (2018), appropriate bookkeeping and accounting systems are important for a successful management of a business be it large or small. The necessity of recording all the transactions enable business to compare results of one period to another period. The bookkeeping and accounting systems impacts on the growth of micro and small enterprises in terms of level of sales, size of the business and level of profitability. Hence, if there is poor or lack of bookkeeping and accounting system the enterprises business is hurted and it incurs more running expenses.

With regard to inappropriate use of credit the mean value has 1.41 and standard deviation of 1.201. This shows Credits or loans for micro and small enterprises are essential for starting the new business for buying raw materials and equipment and used for expanding the existing activity. healthy credits are vital for the enterprises to be profitable and competitive in providing goods and services. According to Amadasun and Mutezo,(2022) inappropriate use of credits have an effect on the financial performance of the enterprises because credits are assets that need to generate returns for an organization and when credits given out are not properly used it lead to the failure of the enterprises.

As indicated in the table on the Shortage of working capital have a better role to the MSEs sustainability the response of mean value is 1.49 and standard deviation of 1.063. Working capital has played an important in achieving profitability for micro and small enterprises. The ability of the enterprises to operate for longer time depends upon a proper access of working capital. A major cause for the failure of micro and small enterprises could be shortage of working capital. This result supported by different studies. businesses that started with at a higher beginning investment expand quicker than those that started with a lower first investment or in other words it implies that enterprises which started their business operation with higher initial investment grow faster than their counterparts and they have better sustainability experience (Beza,2022).

Table 4.4 factors related to the Technological factors of enterprises.

No	TG	Mean	Std.dev.
1.	Access to Information technology and internet	1.65	1.118
2.	Lack of appropriate machinery and equipment	1.50	0.989

Source: survey data, 2023

This table shows questions regarding technological factors to assure micro and small enterprises sustainability. Between them Access to Information technology and internet has a high mean value of 1.65 and standard deviation 1.118. The result indicates that Information technology and internet have a better role to ensure the sustainability of micro and small enterprises. In a competitive business environment the role of information technology (IT) and internet is significant in the process of providing services, products, and packages effectively to achieve a competitive advantage over competitors. And it is the major indicator to determine the enterprises sustainability.

Based on Mizan Sibhatu(2018) information is the ‘life blood’ for business enterprises. Organizations cannot survive without information. They need information on market, raw materials, government directions and others. Providing business information services has been identified as one area that needs attention from the enterprises managers and business services providers that contributed to their daily marketing and production activities. Many firms in Africa Operate in an information-poor environment due to lack of adequate government business support services and the poor information technological infrastructures. Hence, information technology and internet enable the enterprises to increase efficiency, productivity, increase profitability, faster communications and reaching new clients. Besides Access to information technology and internet, lack of appropriate machinery and equipment is the other problem of MSEs engaged in manufacturing, construction and food processing enterprises. MSEs which owe a variety of working machines, equipment and tools, most of which are Welding machine, singer, grinder, stove, drill machine, screw driver, hammer, chisel and clamps helped the enterprises to produce more products and services .

Table 4.5. Factors related to the Work Related factors of enterprises.

No	WR	Mean	Std. dev.
1.	Lack of accessibility of electricity and water	1.54	1.131
2.	Lack of access to working and selling place	1.54	1.097
3.	Inappropriate business location	1.66	1.192

Source: Survey Data, 2023

The first question regarding Lack of accessibility of electricity and water have a contribution to the MSEs sustainability. Among the participants the mean value is 1.54 and standard deviation of 1.131. This indicates that access of electricity and water are important for the sustainability of micro and small enterprises. Furthermore, Habtamu (2013) indicated that MSE's operating with available infrastructure facilities has higher probability of long lasting existence and growth as compared to those MSEs that are operating without adequate infrastructures; and electric power interruption and inadequate water supply in Ethiopia was highly affected the growth of the business. Water and electric infrastructure problems affect especially the manufacturing, construction and service sector. According to Admasu (2012) on his research found out that electric power interruption is the main problem followed by lack of sufficient and quick transportation service hinder the business performance of all sectors. Insufficient and interrupted water supply and lack of appropriate dry waste and sewerage system are the main challenges that hinder the performance of business.

With regard to Lack of access to working and selling place the respondents mean value is 1.54 and standard deviation of 1.097. This shows that Lack of access to working and selling place have an effect to the MSEs sustainability. Lack of infrastructure such as lack of access to land or work place/shade and inappropriate business location are the challenges that affect the sustainability and growth of MSEs in the study area. The empirical findings of Beza Muche(2022) revealed that access to infrastructure is a crucial determinant in MSEs success, since MSEs that are operating at their own working premise grow faster than those that operates at rented and at family working premise. This implies that, MSEs having better access to adequate infrastructure expand quicker than their competitors. As a result, access to infrastructure (such as access to working premises, proximity to raw materials and having enabling working environments) has a positive and considerable impact on MSE sustainability.

In item three, the respondents are asked about Inappropriate business location have a greater impact to the MSEs sustainability. The mean value is 1.66 and standard deviation of 1.192. from this inappropriate business location is the main problem and have a great impact to the sustainability of micro and small enterprises. This idea supported by different authors and studies. Accessibility of a location is the ease with which it can be accessed by different modes of transport. Divergent from these aspects, however, most of the studied area is situated far from the main asphalt road and the condition of the road leading to the cluster from the main road is extremely poor. This poor state of the road condition of locality has culminated in high transportation service costs to the MSEs, in addition to making the sector difficult for accessibility by the existing and potential customers Admasu

Abera(2012).Hence, business location plays a huge role in attracting and retaining the best customers and it makes the enterprises products and services more accessible.

Table 4.6 factors related to Political Legal Factors.

No	PL	Mean	Std.dev
1.	Lack of government support	1.62	1.114
2.	Lack of accessible information on government regulations	1.68	1.193

Source: Survey Data, 2023

From the above question of Lack of accessible information on government regulations has a significant effect on determining micro and small enterprises sustainability. Between them Lack of accessible information on government regulations has high mean value 1.68 and standard deviation of 1.193. This indicates that the existences of Lack of accessible information on government regulations have great influence to the sustainability of micro and small enterprises. As Beza(2022) Political-legal variables such as lack of government support, tax and lack of accessible information on government regulations are the major political and legal factors that determine the sustainability and growth of MSEs in Ethiopia. Furthermore, poor business environment, and policy and regulatory barriers are among the common challenges’ MSEs are facing in Ethiopia. Besides this lack of government support is another problem that affects the performance of enterprises engaged in manufacturing and construction sector. This arises either from the deliberate tendency of the executives to be bureaucratic or their lack of awareness about the peculiar procedures, policies and proclamations that favor MSEs.

Table 4.7 factors related to the Marketing factors of enterprises.

No	MK	Mean	Std. dev.
1.	Lack of available market information	1.49	1.015
2.	Lack of promotion and awareness creation	1.58	1.095
3.	Lack of market linkage	1.53	1.039
4	Poor customer handling system	1.51	0.977

Source: Survey Data, 2023

The first question regarding Lack of available market information have an effect to the MSEs sustainability. Among the participants the mean value is 1.49 and standard deviation of 1.015. This indicates that Lack of available market information have an effect for the sustainability of micro and small enterprises. Market is the major constraint that highly hinders the enterprises performance and sustainability for all sectors in the MSEs. Market information on the enterprises goods and service has become an important tool globally to remain in competitive market and to maximize profit. Market information is vital to the enterprises to minimize the impact of the competition and providing quality product that satisfies customer needs, offering affordable price and engaging in wider distribution. Furthermore, Cheru(2021) indicated that marketing information is an enterprises manager daily activity that is designed to support marketing decisions. The result of the study shows that access to marketing information is important for the sustainability of MSEs. Since we live in an era of the information, marketing manager and enterprise managers must access timely information on prices and quantities that plays a crucial role in reducing the risk of losing money on a market transactions.

In item two on Lack of promotion and awareness creation about the product/services have a major and better impact to the MSEs sustainability with the mean value of 1.58 and standard deviation of 1.095. This indicates that Lack of promotion and awareness creation about the product/services have a better impact to the MSEs sustainability. According Salfiyau(2021) market promotion and awareness creation appears as an issue of how to create an optimal mix of marketing communication tool in order to get a products message and brand from the producer to the consumer. Integrated marketing links public relations, advertizing, direct marketing, bazaars and exhibition in a coordinated fasion. Without effective market promotion and awareness creation the enterprises product/service awareness may remain low in the market and lead to lower than expected revenue. Even if marketing promotion and awareness creation requires budget it helps the enterprises to drive additional revenue.

Besides lack of promotion and awareness creation, Lack of market linkage have an influence to the MSEs sustainability. Among the respondents the mean value is 1.53 and standard deviation of 1.039. This indicates that Lack of market linkage have an influence to the sustainability of micro and small enterprises. According to the federal micro and small scale enterprises development agency(FeMSEDA)of Ethiopia, improving the productivity and market linkage of MSE operators is widely accepted as the engine of MSE development and expansion, providing a pathway to lift a large number of youths out of poverty(FeMSEDA,2015).the government has paid due attention to the

promotion and development of MSE to alleviate the problems related to market linkage and to promote their sustainability. Beza(2022) indicates that Businesses with greater ties to a range of organizations grow more quickly than their competitors . SME and the large purchasing firm both gain from a market linkages approach (helping the creation of long-term commercial partnerships between SME suppliers and larger buyer enterprises). Through this approach, More SMEs receive more and /or cheaper dollar They purchase needed services, they change business practices and / or improve productivity, they increase cost efficiency, Increase profit, Increase employment, they increase sales, they improve product quality and /or product offerings and SMEs’ can achieve a stable market for their products and services.

The fourth question regarding Poor customer handling system, the mean value is 1.51 and standard deviation of 0.977. This indicates that Poor customer handling system have an effect for the sustainability of micro and small enterprises. The ability to effectively handle and solve customer complaints and problems is necessary for customer service associations. Customers who do complain and get their problem effectively solved often develop a strong emotional loyalty to the enterprises. Furthermore, Alene(2020) indicated that poor customer service can not only impact the present or future sales standard but can negatively impact a business in a variety of ways. This is especially true for businesses that rely on experienced business and positive word of mouth advertising for its success. The result of the study shows that poor customer handling system has an effect for the sustainability of MSEs. Since poor customer handling causes customer dissatisfaction, difficulty to attract new customers, incurs additional costs and losing revenue.

4.4 Sustainability measures

Table 4.8 sustainability factors

No	SMSE	Mean	Std.d ev
1.	Profitability of enterprises	2.58	1.561
2.	Market share of enterprises	2.48	1.267

Source: Survey Data, 2023

From the above question of profitability of the enterprises has a significant effect on measuring micro and small enterprises sustainability. The respondents are asked about profitability of the enterprises and expansion in market share has a significant effect on measuring micro and small enterprises sustainability. Between them profitability of the enterprises has a high mean value of 2.58 and standard deviation of 1.561. This indicates that profitability of the enterprises has a significant effect on measuring micro and small enterprises sustainability. Micro and small enterprises confront a considerable number of challenges to their business operations. One of their initiatives to be competitive is becoming profitable in their products or services. In this regard, Devi Andriyani, 2021 cited in his research that one indicator of the level of business profitability is the number of sales, the higher the level of sales is, the better the impact on business sustainability in the long term and the demand to continually keep going business. Hence profitability of enterprises expressed in the growth of their business, existence of high production and innovation and expansion of market share that lead to the enterprises sustainability.

4.5 Level of determinate Factors

To determine the effect level of each factor the researcher were used descriptive statistics of grand mean and standard deviation. The result is indicated in the table below:

Table 4.9 Overall Mean of Each Determinant Factor

No	Sustainability determinants	Mean	Std.deviation	Rank
1.	Management factor	2.65	1.141	1 st
2.	Financial factor	2.61	1.130	2 nd
3.	Marketing factor	2.55	1.054	3 rd
4	Technological factor	2.48	1.090	6 th
5	Work related factor	2.52	1.10	4 th
6	Political legal factor	2.50	1.063	5 th

Source: Survey Data, 2023

As shown from the above table the mean and standard deviation of each determining factor were represented. The determinant factor with the highest mean score is management factor in 2.65 followed by financial factors 2.61, marketing factors 2.55, work related factors 2.52, political factors 2.50 and technological factors 2.48. With this, we can infer that the management factors in micro and small enterprises have a positive and high effect on the micro and small enterprises sustainability. This result

was supported by interviews of key informants from the total 12 response 10 of the researchers interviewed participants agreed management factor is the major for micro and small enterprises sustainably. The reason for this providing training to managers and to employees ,addressing caizen and other management systems, providing reinforcement and corrective measures to reduce risk and increase revenue, improving managers communicative skill, improving managers decision making skill, strengthening Basic managerial function, improving managers strategic business planning skills and articulating goals, improving managers skill of providing division of duties and responsibility among employees and so on...

4.6 Analysis of the Regression model SPSSS Output Result

The main focus of this study is an identifying the determinants of Micro and Small Enterprises Sustainability and the relationship between the dependent and independent variables. The first testing examines that the regression model for identifying the determinants while the second assessment analyze the Spearman rank correlation coefficient for finding the strength of impact of multiple independent variables on a dependent variable.

4.6.1 Diagnosis test of primary data

Before running to test the models, the data sets were tested for the multiple linear regression model assumptions. Therefore, the data were normality assumptions and the assumption of multicollinearity tests are discussed below.

According to Black K. (2010) in his book of —Business Statistics‖ Multicollinearity is when two or more of the independent variables of a multiple regression model are highly correlated. Technically, if two of the independent variables are correlated, we have collinearity; when three or more independent variables are correlated, we have multicollinearity. One of the techniques that attempt to control for the problem of multicollinearity is a variance inflation factor, in which a regression analysis is conducted to predict an independent variable by the other independent variables. In this case, the independent variable being predicted becomes Determinants of Micro and Small Enterprises Sustainability. As this process is done for each of the independent variables, it is possible to determine whether any of the independent variables are a function of the other independent variables, yielding evidence of multicollinearity. Therefore, the researcher used the variance inflation factor (VIF) and the tolerance value tests to verify multicollinearity. According to Black K., (2010) highlight that a VIF of more than 10 points and a tolerance value of less than 0.2 points rules out harmful multicollinearity. Thus, the result shows in (table

4.9) that the value of tolerance value is greater than 0.2 points and a VIF value is less than 10 points. Therefore, there is no multicollinearity problem between the variables.

Table 4.10 Multicollinearity Test

Model		Collinearity Statistics	
		Tolerance	VIF
1	(Constant)		
	MG	.299	3.344
	FC	.221	4.527
	WR	.275	3.631
	TC	.278	3.603
	MK	.743	1.346
	PL	.283	2.763

Source: SPSS result 2023

4.6.2 Determinant variables that are significant predictors of Micro and Small Enterprises sustainability

Table 4.11 Coefficients^a

Coefficients ^a						
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	T	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	.980	.030		33.079	.000
	MG	.994	.135	.953	7.362	.000
	FC	.992	.175	.940	5.669	.000
	TG	.359	.131	.346	2.738	.000
	MK	.806	.117	.764	6.895	.000
	PL	.563	.082	.641	6.865	.036
	WR	-.803	.092	.687	-8.731	.041

a. Dependent Variable: sustainability

b. Independent Variables; Management Factor (MG), Financial Factor (FC) Technological Factor (TG), Marketing Factors (MK), Work related Factor (WR) and Political Factor (PL)

Hypothesis1: Work related factor has a positive and significant effect on Micro and Small Enterprise sustainability.

Ho = There is no positive and significant relationship between work related factor and Micro and Small Enterprise sustainability. Reject Ho since P-value of Work related factor is 0.041 statistically significant because the level of significance is less than α -value 0.05. At 5% level of significance there is a significant relationship between work related factor and micro and small enterprises sustainability. That is Work related factor is significantly affects micro and small enterprises sustainability. From the above table the estimated coefficient of Work related factor is -0.803. Holding other independent variable constant, the more complicated work related situation undermines effective micro and small enterprises sustainability by 80.3%. When there is negative relationship between work related factor and micro and small enterprises sustainability, this implies that when government addresses infrastructural facilities it makes the operators to be dependent, and when these infrastructures are interrupted, their service delivery is interrupted and their productivity decreases. when we cut down work related factors, it empowers the enterprises to solve the problems on their own and increases their profitability and helps to create improved systems.

Hypothesis2: Management Factors has a positive and significant effect on Micro and Small Enterprise sustainability.

Ho = There is no positive and significant relationship between management factor and micro and small enterprises sustainability.

H1= There is a significant relationship between management factor and micro and small enterprises sustainability. Reject Ho since P-value of Management factor is 0.000. It is statistically significant because the level of significance is less than α -value 0.05. At 5% level of significance there is a significant relationship between Management factor and micro and small enterprises sustainability. That is Management Factors has a significant effect on Micro and Small Enterprise sustainability. From the above table the estimated coefficient of management factor is 0.994. Holding other independent variable constant, the more management factor results in a 99.4% increases the micro and small enterprises sustainability. The Management Factor is stronger on micro and small enterprises sustainability than other independent variables.

Hypothesis3: Technological Factor has positive influence on Micro and Small Enterprise sustainability.

Ho = There is no positive and significant relationship between Technological Factor and Micro and Small Enterprises Sustainability.

H1= There is a significant relationship between Technological Factor and Micro and Small Enterprises Sustainability. Reject Ho since P-value of Technological Factor is 0.000. It is statistically significant because the level of significance is less than α -value 0.05. At 5% level of significance there is a significant relationship between Technological Factor and Micro and Small Enterprises Sustainability. That is Technological Factor has positive influence on Micro and Small Enterprises sustainability. From the above table the estimated coefficient of Technological Factor is 0.359. Holding other independent variable constant, the more Technology expands 35.9% increases the micro and small enterprises sustainability.

Hypothesis4: Financial Factor has positive influence on Micro and Small Enterprise sustainability.

Ho = There is no positive and significant relationship between Financial Factors and micro and small enterprises sustainability.

H1= There is a significant relationship between Financial Factors and micro and small enterprises sustainability. Reject Ho since P-value of Financial Factor is 0.000. It is statistically significant because the level of significance is less than α -value 0.05. At 5% level of significance there is a significant relationship between Financial Factors and micro and small enterprises sustainability. That is Financial Factor has positive influence on Micro and Small Enterprise sustainability. From the above table the estimated coefficient of Financial Factors is 0.992. Holding other independent variable constant, the more accessing credit and finance results in a 99.2% increases the micro and small enterprises sustainability.

Hypothesis5 Marketing Factor has a positive and significant effect on Micro and Small Enterprise sustainability.

Ho = There is no positive and significant relationship between Marketing Factor and micro and small enterprises sustainability.

H1= There is a significant relationship between Marketing Factor and micro and small enterprises sustainability. Reject Ho since P-value of Marketing Factor is 0.000. It is statistically significant because the level of significance is less than α -value 0.05. At 5% level of significance there is a significant relationship between Marketing Factor and micro and small enterprises sustainability. That

is Marketing Factor has a significant influence on Micro and Small Enterprise sustainability. From the above table the estimated coefficient of Marketing Factor is 0.806. Holding other independent variable constant, the more implementing Marketing Factor results in 80.6% increases the micro and small enterprises sustainability.

Hypothesis6 Political Factor has positive influence on Micro and Small Enterprise sustainability.

Ho = There is no positive and significant relationship between Political Factor and micro and small enterprises sustainability.

H1= There is a significant relationship between Political Factor and micro and small enterprises sustainability. Reject Ho since P-value of Political Factor is 0.036. It is statistically significant because the level of significance is less than α -value 0.05. At 5% level of significance there is a significant relationship between Political Factor and micro and small enterprises sustainability. That is Political Factor has positive influence on Micro and Small Enterprise sustainability. From the above table the estimated coefficient of Political Factor is 0.563. Holding other independent variable constant, the more government support exists result in 56.3% increases the micro and small enterprises sustainability. Generally the hypothesis are expressed as bellows

Table 4.12 Summary of Hypothesis Testing Result

Code	Hypothesis	Test result/Relation	Decision
H1	Management Factors has a significant effect on Micro and Small Enterprise sustainability.	Positive/significant	Accept
H2	Technological Factor has positive influence on Micro and Small Enterprise sustainability.	Positive/significant	Accept
H3	Financial Factor has positive influence on Micro and Small Enterprise sustainability.	Positive/significant	Accept
H4	Marketing Factor has a significant effect on Micro and Small Enterprise sustainability.	Positive/significant	Accept
H5	Political Factor has positive influence on Micro and Small Enterprise sustainability.	Positive/significant	Accept
H6	Work related factor has positive and significant effect on Micro and Small Enterprise sustainability.	Negative/significant	Accept H0

From the above coefficient table the multiple regression equation is:

$$SMSE = 0.980 + 0.994MG + 0.992FC + 0.359TG + 0.806MK + 0.563PL - 0.803 + 0.51$$

4.6.3 Percentage of the variation in micro and small enterprises sustainability is explained by the independent variables

Table 4.13 Model Summary^b

Model Summary ^b				
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.974 ^a	.949	.948	.24549
a. Predictors: (Constant), work related, management, political, marketing, technological, financial b. Dependent Variable: Sustainability				

Source: SPSS result 2023

Explained Variation (R^2) is only 0.949 that is 94.9%. From the above table 4.11 we have to understand that $R^2 = 0.949$, this indicated that 94.9% of Micro and Small Enterprises Sustainability is explained and determined jointly by independent variables that is Work related Factor, Management Factor, Political Factor, Marketing Factor, Technological Factor, and Financial Factor, but 5.1% dependent variable SMSE explained by other variables that are not included in the model.

CHAPTER FIVE

SUMMARY OF FINDINGS, CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

5.1. Summary of Findings

The study was conducted to assess the determinants of Micro and Small Enterprises sustainability in Rebu Gebeya Town. Three research objectives guided the study. Research objective one sought to examine the effect of internal determinants that influence the sustainability of micro and small enterprises, research objective two sought to determine the effect of external determinants that influence the sustainability of micro and small enterprises, research objective three sought to assess the level of micro and small enterprises sustainability. To answer the above-mentioned objective the researcher largely used primary data through conducting stratified random sampling techniques. To assess the determinants of micro and small enterprises sustainability in Rebu Gebeya Town from micro and small enterprises. Data were collected from five major micro and small enterprise sectors, these are manufacturing, urban agriculture, construction, trade and service and from 240 respondents. The data was analyzed by using frequency, percentages, mean, standard deviation, correlation and statistics regression analysis methods. The distribution of the respondents by sex and age shows that the majorities 190(79.2%) of the respondents were male and 189 (78.75%) of the respondents were found between age (18-33) years. Regarding the educational level of the respondents, 216 (90%) of them had completed from grade 1 up to degree.

The objective of the study was determining the factors related to micro and small enterprises sustainability. About this, the respondents were asked many questions. Based on the respondents perception the highest mean score is Management factor in 2.65 followed by Financial factors 2.61 Marketing factors 2.55, Work related factor 2.52, Political factor 2.50 and Technological factor 2.48. With this, we can infer that the Management factors in micro and small enterprises have a positive and high effect on the micro and small enterprises sustainability.

5.2 Conclusions

The research has explored determinants of micro and small enterprises sustainability in Rebu Gebeya Town with the primary intention of examining the determinants of the sustainability of MSEs engaged in manufacturing, urban agriculture, construction, trade and service sectors. Accordingly, based on the research questions framed in the study, the conclusion was found to be appealing and practical to integrate the issue of micro and small enterprises sustainability. The major points are précised as follows;

The role of micro and small enterprises is consistently recognized in employment and income generating and enhancing growth and alleviating poverty. The finding result shows that the internal factors that determine MSEs sustainability is management factors whereas the external factors that determine MSEs sustainability are financial, marketing, political legal, work related and technological factors.

According to Black K., (2010) highlight that a VIF of more than 10 points and a tolerance value of less than 0.2 points rules out harmful multicollinearity. Thus, the result shows in (table 4.10) that the value of tolerance value is greater than 0.2 points and a VIF value is less than 10 points. Therefore, there is no multicollinearity problem between the variables.

The output of regression model that $R^2=0.949$ this indicated that 94.9% of micro and small enterprises Sustainability is explained by independent variables that is management factor, financial factor, work related factor, marketing factor, technological factors and political factor but 5.1% dependent variable SMSE explained by other variables that are not included in the model.

The ANOVA result show that sig. value is 0.000 is less than 0.05 significance level. From this result we have to understand that one of the independent variables (Management factor, Financial factor, Work related factor, Marketing factor, Technological factors and Political factor) explains the dependent variable (micro and small enterprises sustainability).

The result of Test on Regression Coefficients illustrate that Management factor, Financial factor, Work related factor, Marketing factor, Technological factors and Political factor are the major determinants of micro and small enterprises sustainability. The Management Factors is stronger on micro and small enterprises sustainability than other independent variables. Because the Standardized Coefficients of Management Factors beta is 0.994 it is greater than the other. According to the result of the respondents micro and small enterprises sustainability is measured by the enterprises profitability. When there is high access in work related, marketing, technological and financial factors and solving in management

problems and addressing political legal supports to the enterprises that help to increase the enterprises profitability.

According to the Spearman's rank correlation, Positive correlations near +1 indicate that high values of one variable tend to be associated with high values of the other variable. Thus, the correlations indicate positive and management factor, financial factor, marketing factor, work related factor, political factor and technological factor has relatively high value and positive correlation for micro and small enterprises sustainability whereas work related factor is negatively correlated to the micro and small enterprises sustainability that empowers the enterprises to solve work related problems on their own, increases profitability and to create improved processes

5.3 Recommendations

Based on the findings and conclusions, the following recommendations are forwarded with the hope that they could be used by organizations that work with Micro and Small Enterprises development and other concerned bodies.

- Management Factors are major determinant factors of micro and small enterprises sustainability. Therefore, to reduce the negative effect of management factor and to guarantee the sustainability of the micro and small enterprises Woreda Administration Work and Training Office, and other concerned bodies should focus to solve or minimize the enterprises internal or management factor of absence of harmonious relationship among employees/team work, Lack of clear division of duties and responsibility among employees, lack of Proper planning and poor management problems by the enterprises themselves rather than waiting third party solutions.
- Political leaders and professionals play a vital role in improving the sustainability of micro and small enterprise and increasing their profitability. Thus, the Office and stakeholders should design and implement strategies that could increase micro and small enterprises sustainability with efficiency and effectiveness.
- Because of the increasing demand for micro and small enterprise product and service woreda administration and work and training office should give special attention to provide support in making market linkage to their products, access finance, give intervention to solve infrastructural factors particularly electricity and working and selling sheds.
- As we are seeing in practice that micro and small enterprises are the door for the exit of poverty in developing countries. Majority of the problems in relation to the enterprises sustainability

arise from government policies and strategies. Thus the focus should be on solving work related constraints and pursuing alternative supportive mechanisms of deregulating the financial sector for the enterprises development practices.

Finally, the researcher recommends a more detailed and comprehensive investigation in the same area among other populations to identify the determinants of Micro and Small Enterprises Sustainability

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APPENDIX

Appendix I - Questionnaire

Appendix “A”

Debre Markos University

College of Business and Economics

Department of Management

Title: Determinants of The Sustainability of Micro and Small Enterprises; The Case of MSEs in Rob Gebeya Town.

1. To be filled by the enterprises

Note - There is no need of writing your name.

- Please read each question provided below and tick (✓) inside the boxes

Corresponding to the response that defines you and/or most accurately reflects your views.

-You can also express your views in the available space where necessary

Part one: Background of respondents

Put “x” Infront of your choice

1. Sex female male
2. Age 18-25 26-33 34- 51 52 and above
3. Marital status : single married divorces widowed
4. Education level :No formal Education 0/12 completed and below diploma
 degree masters others
5. Main activity of the enterprise: manufacturing construction urban agriculture
 trade ice
6. How Long you have been working in the enterprise; 5 years and below 6 to 10 years
 11 to 15 years 16 years and above

Part Two: Determinants of MSE Sustainability

The major Determinants that affect the Sustainability of MSEs are listed below. Please indicate the degree to which these Determinants are affecting the Sustainability of your business enterprise. After you read each of the Determinants, evaluate them in relation to your business and then put a tick mark (√) under the choices below. Where, 5 = strongly agree, 4 = agree, 3 = Neither agree nor disagree, 2 = disagree and 1= strongly disagree.

- ❖ Please rate your level of agreement based on the represented scales provided in the table: **where (1=strongly disagree; 2 =Disagree; 3= Neither agree nor disagree ; 4= Agree; 5=strongly agree)**

N O.	Questions related to Management factors	Level of rating				
		1	2	3	4	5
1	Lack of strategic business planning on your business					
2	Lack of clear division of duties and responsibility among employees					

3	Poor management skill					
4	Lack of harmonious relationships among team work					
5	Managers education level on your business					
6	Family size of enterprises					

❖ Please rate your level of agreement based on the represented scales provided in the table: **where (1=strongly disagree; 2 =Disagree; 3= Neither agree nor disagree ; 4= Agree; 5=strongly agree)**

NO.	Questions related to Financial factors	Level of rating				
		1	2	3	4	5
1	Lack of access to finance					
2	Poor Book keeping and accounting system					
3	Inappropriate use of credit					
4	Shortage of working capital					

❖ Please rate your level of agreement based on the represented scales provided in the table: **where (1=strongly disagree; 2 =Disagree; 3= Neither agree nor disagree ; 4= Agree; 5=strongly agree)**

NO.	Questions related to Work related factors	Level of rating				
		1	2	3	4	5
1	Lack of accessibility of electricity and water					
2	Lack of access to working and selling place					
3	Inappropriate business location					

- ❖ Please rate your level of agreement based on the represented scales provided in the table: **where (1=strongly disagree; 2 =Disagree; 3= Neither agree nor disagree ; 4= Agree; 5=strongly agree)**

No	Questions related to technological factors	Level of rating				
		1	2	3	4	5
1	Access for Information technology and internet					
2	Lack of appropriate machinery and equipment					

- ❖ Please rate your level of agreement based on the represented scales provided in the table: **where (1=strongly disagree; 2 =Disagree; 3= Neither agree nor disagree ; 4= Agree; 5=strongly agree)**

No	Questions related to marketing factors	Level of rating				
		1	2	3	4	5
1	Poor customer handling system					
2	Lack of available market information					
3	Lack of promotion and awareness creation about the product/services					
4	Lack of market linkage					

- ❖ Please rate your level of agreement based on the represented scales provided in the table: **where (1=strongly disagree; 2 =Disagree; 3= Neither agree nor disagree ; 4= Agree; 5=strongly agree)**

No	Questions related to political factors	Level of rating				
		1	2	3	4	5
1	Lack of government support					
2	Lack of accessible information on government regulations that are relevant to your business					

PART THREE; The effect of general factors on micro and small enterprises sustainability

No	Questions related to general factors	Level of rating				
		1	2	3	4	5
1	Management factors					
2	Financial factors					
3	Technological factors					
4	Work related factors					
5	Political legal factors					
6	Marketing factors					

PART FOUR; Sustainability measures

No	Questions related to sustainability	Level of rating				
		1	2	3	4	5
1	Profitability of the enterprise					
2	Market share of the enterprise					